

PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 3 LEARNERS IN MATHEMATICS UNDER MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING MODALITY

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the Mathematics performance of Grade 3 learners at Central 1 Elementary School under the modular distance learning modality during the school year 2021-2022. There are 46.9% of the learners whose performance level in mathematics is average and 37.5% have a high level of performance. The overall performance level of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics is Average with a mean score of 17.88. There is a significant relationship between the module time exposure of the Grade 3 learners and performance level in Mathematics. Moreover, there is also a significant relationship between facilitators' highest educational attainment and their performance level in Mathematics. Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for a possible course of action. First, Teachers should coordinate with parents and guide the learners to spend more time practicing their exercises in their Self-Learning Modules to enhance their Mathematics or calculation skills. Second, Teachers should provide practice exercises and integrate scheduled time for mathematics activities in the SLMs that may help the learners enjoy learning at home. Third, Further studies should be conducted to include other factors not covered in this study that may affect the Mathematics performance among learners. Lastly, similar studies should be conducted in other learning areas of the curriculum to focus on other variables and grade levels of learners under the distance learning modality.

Keywords. Modular Distance Learning Modality, Acceptability Level, Module Time Exposure

1 Introduction

According to Grace Fleming (2015), the first mathematical building blocks are established during primary school when students learn the rules of addition and multiplication and these first concepts comprise the foundation. The next building blocks come in the succeeding grade levels when students first learn about formulas and operations. It is important, therefore, that students have a firm grasp of the basic concepts of Mathematics so they do not get lost because of the complexity and difficulty of the subject.

However, despite the complexity and difficulty of Mathematics, it is said that Mathematics plays an important role not only within the four corners of the classroom but even beyond. Knowledge of Mathematics is indispensable in everyday life and is very much necessary for higher learning and research. As aptly put in the K to 12 Curriculum Guide by the Department of Education, Mathematics is one subject that pervades life at any stage and in any circumstances. Moreover, a lack of sufficient mathematical skills and understanding affects one's ability to make critically important educational, life, and career decisions. Mathematics as a subject therefore must be learned comprehensively and with great depth.

In the school year 2020-2021, face-to-face learning engagement of students and teachers within the school has been suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This pandemic has paved the way for the implementation of Modular Distance Learning as an urgent response to ensure continuity of education. The Philippines is in the process of adapting to the new normal form of education at present, and continuous innovations of educators and the active involvement of other stakeholders are the driving force for its success.

Modular learning is the most popular type of Distance Learning. It is considered highly convenient for most of the typical Filipino students. Modular Distance Learning is also the most preferred learning system of the majority of parents/guardians based on the result of the Learning Enrollment and Survey Form (LESF). This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where the internet is not accessible for online learning. The teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners. The learners may ask assistance from the teacher via e-mail, telephone, text

message/instant messaging among others. Where possible, the teacher shall do home visits to learners needing remediation or assistance (Llego, n.d.).

For the second year of implementing modular distance learning in education, there are a lot of challenges concerning modular learning that came out. Both the learners and the teachers are at a disadvantage. First, modules are not substitutes for teachers. The module relies on their knowledge and patience to teach the students whatever concept they don't understand. Lessons are limited to what is written on paper. So, without a knowledgeable person who can explain confusing or complicated concepts written in the module (especially in Math, English, and Science subjects), the student won't understand it. The learners will have difficulty absorbing their lessons. It is hard to absorb new information when no one is there to guide you (or at least empathize with you) when the lessons become too much. This may also contribute to the anxiety and depression of some learners who feel now that they're struggling to keep up with modular learning demands. Although both the teachers and the students are trying their best to perform well in this situation, it's just not ideal. With the current setup DepEd has for its teachers and students, the possibility of anyone genuinely learning anything is low.

Second, examples are limited. The modules themselves aren't perfect. They differ from school to school, and their contents depend on the teachers who prepared them. Some of the modules given had numerous examples but there are some errors and inaccuracies that peppered news reports and social media feeds last year. Learners may not have a problem understanding their lessons because of a well-explained module, but others may not be as lucky. With the lack of standard books used, the level of learning varies.

Third, there is a lack of feedback. Once modules have been answered and delivered to the teacher, students only have to worry about the next modules coming in. There is little to no feedback regarding what they have learned and if their answers are correct. Therefore, the modular approach becomes an endless stream of paperwork for both the student and the teacher with no way of knowing its effectiveness.

According to some parents interviewed by the researcher, despite the adjustments made under the new modes of learning, they think learners are learning, but learning with teachers is far way better. Face-to-face classes are still the best way to go. Moreover, they spend more time assisting their child in answering their modules, especially in Mathematics subject to explain the concepts because they find it hard to understand the lessons. Thus, remote education posed a major challenge for learners who did not have anyone to facilitate learning at home, or whose facilitators (parents or guardians) are not capable of guiding them due to lack of knowledge.

Given the current situation, the researcher decided to conduct this study to determine the performance of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics under modular distance learning modality to assess or monitor the learner's progress and to improve the teaching and learning process. The researcher believes that the results of this study will enable parents to become aware of their children's performance and consequently of the learners. This can be a call for the Department of Education to address some issues and challenges regarding the performance of learners in Mathematics and other learning areas.

2 Review of Related Literature

The studies of Maloney et al. and Morada investigated Mathematics achievement or Mathematics performance of learners and how it relates to the numerical anxiety of the students themselves and their parents. Similarly, the present study determined learners' performance in Mathematics but it differs from the previous studies in terms of the profile variables to which Mathematics performance is correlated.

In their study, Ajai and Imoko worked on the Problem-Based Learning method and students' achievement in Algebra. Teaching was done in a traditional classroom setting. The present study, on the other hand, deals with Grade 3 learners' performance in Mathematics under the Modular distance learning modality in which SLMs were utilized by the learners in studying their lessons facilitated by their parent or guardian.

The present study is similar to the study of Cordova and Tan in determining the relationship between Mathematics performance and certain variables such as parents' educational attainment and family income. They also correlated in

Mathematics performance with gender and Mathematics proficiency which the present study did not include as profile variables. Instead, the present study, in context due to the prevailing situation, involved module time exposure, extent of facilitator's assistance, and availability and frequency of Mathematics learning materials at home as profile variables of the Grade 3 learners under modular distance learning modality. Both studies had Grade 3 learners as subjects of study but they differ in terms of locale and mode of learning.

Ocomen's (2016) study on the performance of Grade 1 pupils in Mathematics is similar to the present study. They differ in terms of locale and subjects of study. In the study of Ocomen, she used games but in the present study Self learning modules (SLMs) were utilized by the learners in their homes.

The studies of Martinez (2017) and Romaguera (2019) are similar to the present study, in the sense that they focused on the correlation of learners' profiles in terms of some variables and their level of performance in Mathematics. It is also noted that the study of Martinez and the present study were focused on Grade 3 learners, hence both studies used teacher-made tests in their mother tongue as assessment tools in Mathematics. However, they differ in terms of locale, grade level of learners, and modality of learning

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive-correlational method of research. The researcher used this research design to gather information about the present conditions regarding the profile of Grade 3 learners in Central 1 Elementary School and their performance in Mathematics under the modular distance learning modality. It is correlational because it determines the relationship between the variables of the study. According to Creswell (2012), correlational research designs are used by investigators to describe and measure the degree of relationship between two or more variables or sets of scores.

3.2 Sources of Data

The study was conducted in Central 1 Elementary School, located at Roxas Boulevard, San Carlos City, Pangasinan during the school year 2021-2022. The school is under District 1-A of the San Carlos City Division. The subjects of the study involved the population of thirty-two (32) Grade 3 learners of section Mapagmahal in Central 1 Elementary School, San Carlos City, Pangasinan who were enrolled during the School Year 2021-2022.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

On the availability of Mathematics learning materials at home (printed and digitized), frequency counts were used. Regarding the frequency of usage of materials, this was determined using frequency counts and percentages.

For the learners' performance in the different learning content areas in Mathematics such as Numbers up to 10,000 and Addition and Subtraction of Whole Numbers, a test score scale shown below was used to interpret results. There are ten-item questions in each of the learning content in Mathematics.

To answer sub-problem number 3, the χ^2 (Chi-Square) test of association was employed in determining the relationship between the learners' profile variables and their level of performance in Mathematics 3. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used to process the data collected and to determine the statistical measures required in this study.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Performance Level of the Grade 3 Learners in Mathematics

The table discloses that 46.9% or 15 of the total number of Grade 3 learners registered an average performance level in Mathematics. Twelve (12 or 37.5%) have high performance levels. This implies that most of the Grade 3 learners have average ability in Mathematics. It could be inferred that they spend more time studying their SLMs and accomplishing

their learning activities. It can be noted, however, that there are four learners with low levels of performance. Hence, their facilitators should give more assistance to their children in studying their lessons, especially in Mathematics.

Table 1. Performance Level of the Grade 3 Learners in Mathematics
N=32

Performance Level	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Very High	1	3.1
High	12	37.5
Average	15	46.9
Low	4	12.5
Very Low	0	0
Total	32	100

The table presents the mean score and the performance level of the Grade 3 learners. It discloses that the Grade 3 learners in this study have a mean score of 17.88 which falls under the performance level description of "Average". The result implies that the Grade 3 learners can learn basic Mathematics concepts and are capable of doing Mathematics calculations, but they still need assistance in studying their lesson in Mathematics. There is a need to help the learners improve their skills in Mathematics to attain a high or very high level of performance.

4.2 Test of Significance of the Relationship Between Profile of the Grade 3 Learners and their Performance Level in Mathematics

Table 2 shows the correlational analysis between the learners' profile in terms of the variables and their performance level in Mathematics. It can be gleaned from the first highlighted value in the table that there is a significant correlation between the learners' module time exposure and their performance in mathematics ($\chi^2=13.460$, $p<.036$). Since the p-value (.036*) is less than the significance level ($\alpha =.05$), it warrants the researcher to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the Grade 3 learners in terms of module time exposure and their level of performance in Mathematics. The result implies that if the learners spend more time studying their modules, the more likely they improve their performance in Mathematics subject.

Moreover, the table also reveals that the highest educational attainment of the mothers whom learners identified as their facilitators at home has a significant association with their performance in Mathematics ($\chi^2=50.867$, $p<.004$). The result suggests that highly educated facilitators who tend to closely supervise their children in their studies of modules at home can help them achieve higher performance in Mathematics.

In terms of the other variables in the study such as the extent of facilitators assistance ($\chi^2=6.851$, $p=.653$), availability of materials at home (printed, $\chi^2=4.981$, $p=.959$; digitized, $\chi^2=6.255$, $p=.714$), and frequency of usage of materials ($\chi^2=8.369$, $p=.212$), and its association to the learners' performance in Mathematics, the results indicate that the p values are greater than the significance level set at alpha .05. Thus, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis and therefore concludes that there is not enough evidence to suggest a significant relationship between these profile variables and the performance level of the learners in Mathematics.

Therefore, teachers should encourage the facilitators to help the learners spend more time studying the mathematics modules. Moreover, open and constant communication and collaboration between teachers and facilitators could improve the performance of the learners in Mathematics under the modular distance learning modality.

Table 3. Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Digitized Self-Learning Module in Science 7 by Criterion

Profile Variables and Performance Level in Mathematics		<i>X² value and pvalue</i>
Module Time Exposure and Performance Level in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	13.460
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.036*
Highest Educational Attainment of Facilitator and Performance Level in Mathematics <i>Father</i>	Pearson Correlation	20.589
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.150
Highest Educational Attainment of Facilitator and Performance Level in Mathematics <i>Mother</i>	Pearson Correlation	50.867
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004*
Highest Educational Attainment of Facilitator and Performance Level in Mathematics <i>Guardian</i>	Pearson Correlation	11.830
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.692
Extent of Facilitators Assistance and Performance Level in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	6.851
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.653
Availability of Learning Materials at Home and Performance Level in Mathematics <i>Printed</i>	Pearson Correlation	4.981
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.959
Availability of Learning Materials at Home and Performance Level in Mathematics <i>Digitized</i>	Pearson Correlation	6.255
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.714
Frequency of Usage of Materials and Performance Level in Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	8.369
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.212

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

On the profile of the Grade 3 learners, the majority (56.3.6%) of the learners often spend their time studying their module, and the highest educational attainment of the learners' facilitators is college graduates. The result also revealed that 40.6% of the learners' facilitators spend 2 hours a day to assist their child with his/her modular activities. The majority of the learners' available learning materials at home are mathematics textbooks and gadgets which they often use 1-3 times a week. There are 46.9% of the learners whose performance level in mathematics is average and 37.5% have a high level of performance. The overall performance level of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics is Average with a mean score of 17.88.52. There is a significant relationship ($x^2 = 13.460$, $p < .036$) between the module time exposure of the Grade 3 learners and their performance level in Mathematics. Moreover, there is also a significant relationship between facilitators' highest educational attainment ($x^2 = 50.867$, $p < .004$) and their performance level in Mathematics.

A typical Grade 3 learner of Central 1 Elementary School can be described with the following characteristics: He often spends enough time studying SLMs in Mathematics; His mother, the main facilitator of learning in Mathematics is a college graduate and often assists the child in doing his learning activities in the SLMs; He often uses a textbook and utilizes a gadget in studying his Mathematics lessons. The Grade 3 learners have an average ability to understand the concepts and can do basic calculations in Mathematics. There is a need to improve the learners' level of performance in Mathematics. Learners should spend more time and focus on practicing their mathematics skills and studying their modules in Mathematics. Likewise, facilitators should give more time to their children and provide more assistance in their modular learning activities.

Teachers should coordinate with parents and guide the learners to spend more time practicing their exercises in their Self-Learning Modules to enhance their Mathematics or calculation skills. Teachers should provide practice exercises and integrate scheduled time for mathematics activities in the SLMs that may help the learners enjoy learning at home.

Further studies should be conducted to include other factors not covered in this study that may affect the Mathematics performance among learners. Similar studies should be conducted in other learning areas of the curriculum to focus on other variables and grade levels of learners under the distance learning modality.

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